

CoDa based approach to till and surficial geochemistry in mineral exploration

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Geochemical data is considered as compositional data (CoDa) which can be summed up to a fixed constant (e.g., percentages, proportions) and these data contains the ratios between measured components that represent relative information between measurements (Filzmoser et al., 2018). In Finland, three main datasets are available for regional scale research: targeting till, regional till and rock geochemical datasets. The use of those datasets in mineral exploration are going to be considered in this abstract. The targeting till geochemical data set contains around 385 000 till samples collected by the Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) where the sampling density lies between 6-12 samples per km² (Gustavsson et al., 1979). The regional till data which cover the whole Finland has sampling density of one sample per 4 km² including the full data set of 82 062 samples (Salminen & Tarvainen, 1995) and the rock geochemical dataset contains the concentrations of different elements in Finnish bedrock for 6544 samples (Geological Survey of Finland, 2007). A subset of data from the Central Lapland area, Finland has been considered and the targeting till geochemical data set has serious data quality issues, typically connected to values related to detection limits, zeros and even negative analytical results, and values marked with special symbols where extensive data cleaning was required. Q-Q plots were used to evaluate the distribution of concentrations between different map sheets in the regional as well as in the targeting till data sets to analyse the mismatch between map sheets and they vary quite strongly between map sheets in targeting till data for some elements such as Ni, Fe. Moreover, they vary between targeting and regional till data sets despite compositional transformation. Thus, it was decided not to combine the values from the map sheets in the analysis, but to analyse the map sheets (1:100 000 scale) separately, as the small areas contain enough sample points to carry out the analysis. However, the differences between the two data sets might be mainly due to different analytical techniques. PCA maps were generated for a selected area which contains two Ni-Cu-PGE deposits (Sakatti and Kevitsa), by considering all 3 data sets separately. According to PCAs, the loadings for Cu are lower in both targeting and regional till data sets whereas it is higher in the weathered bedrock PCA, which could indicate till transportation. Furthermore, in all three plots Ti, V and Al positively correlate with each other.

Another approach in surficial geochemistry is to test how upper soil weak leach geochemical methods and biogeochemistry is working in tracing the critical metal sources in different soil types and land use areas in Europe. The target areas locate in Czech Republic, Finland, Poland and Portugal. Aims are to test if the deposit is detectable at the surface, influence of the bedrock lithology, and the influence of surface cover on the geochemical signal on thick sediment cover such as a top of esker and typical till cover. Preliminary results of upper soil analysis in Akanvaara test site show a significant response to many elements with known mineralized bedrock targets observed in the drill core data and elemental distribution is also reflecting the lithological variations of the rock units in the bedrock. Based on the results, it is obvious that a) there is good or moderate correlation for several elements between the surface geochemical data and underlying bedrock, and b) soil analysis method using certain soil sampling procedure and selective extraction is an effective, environmentally friendly geochemical exploration technique in the glaciated terrains.

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